

MODERN APPROACHES IN MODERN EDUCATION.

Yusupova Nargiza Nigmatovna

Tashkent state Uzbek language and literature

University "English language"

Department teacher Ph.D

Yusupova_n@navoiy-uni.uz

nargizanigmatovna@gmail.com

tel; 998977702744

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245392>

Abstract. This article describes how to use and apply modern and mixed educational technologies in the process of mixed education. The main focus is on 2 technologies and approaches. Among them, "online homework", "Travel training" and "50+25+25" approach. These modern and new technologies and approaches have proven very effective in our research.

Keywords. "Online homework", "Mobile training" and "50+25+25" approach, blended learning, modern technologies.

Although the study of technology and e-learning is very useful in the 21st century due to the development of information technology, there are also disadvantages in this process, including the problem of the Internet: in some countries, either the Internet connection is too slow, or they do not have enough educational technology. We know from our experience that many students cannot afford to buy gadgets or pay for Internet access. Innovative trends in education do not depend on e-learning and technology, there are methods that a teacher can use to develop the learning process in the classroom and even outside of it. Its implementation, that is, the combination of traditional and innovative methods in these methods, depends on the skill of the teacher. A competency-based approach, teaching problem solving, creative thinking, and research writing is important in this, as well as focusing on:

1. We can note the next technology that was developed and used very effectively during our research - "online homework". It is dedicated to the problem of doing homework as one of the main methods of strengthening, controlling and self-control of the materials learned in the practical lesson as an innovative technology of English language teaching. With the help of the <https://learningapps.org/> internet service, the author performed "Online Homework" with a group of students. It has been proven that it contributes to the popularization of homework among students and improves the quality of knowledge and the ability to work with information. Homework is a necessary element of the educational process, especially in the field of foreign language, because it helps the student to consolidate the acquired knowledge, is a powerful tool for control and self-control. But unfortunately, the demand for homework has disappeared in recent years, and many students are now not motivated enough to do it, because it is often easier for students to use ready-made answer banks or copy from classmates. our witness, which leads to the loss of the importance of homework in the educational process.

For the young people of the new generation, the digital age, they want HEIs to communicate with them in the same language, and one of the ways of communication is

digital technologies. In this regard, one of the main reasons why young people lack motivation to do homework is the retrograde methods of doing it. During the experimental work, we conducted a survey among students from the 1st to the 4th year, asking them: "Are you interested in receiving homework online, through network resources?" As a result of the answer to the question, we were surprised by the large number of supporters of this idea, and we aimed to conduct an experiment on the introduction of online homework in English using the Internet service. To carry out the experiment, the following preliminary steps are required:

- analysis of thematic planning using internet services;
- planning universal educational activities of students;
- formation of goals for using network services (learning new material, strengthening, summarizing material, control);
- analysis and selection of effective types of internet services;
- creating tasks for students to try in practice and giving step-by-step instructions on working with it in YouTube video hosting;
- introduction of Internet services into educational activities as test materials and ways of working with them in training to familiarize students with the service itself;
- performing an experiment as homework;
- the final goal of this experiment is to introduce online homework as a permanent element of the educational system in foreign language classes.

2. During the research, a new author's approach was developed for perfect and easy learning of the English language. This approach repeats the elements of dual education in some aspects. It is known that dual education is a type of specialized education, which gives a student the opportunity to acquire theoretical knowledge in an educational institution, and practical skills in the workplace, that is, in organizations and universities. We tentatively named the new approach we are proposing as "50+25+25". "50+25+25" is not just a sequence of numbers, but a radically different way of looking at 21st century education. In our opinion, the "50+25+25" approach is very effective for the formation and development of professional competencies.

A brief description of this approach that we propose follows. The theoretical, educational and practical part of the educational program is in a professional educational institution, the stage of formation of skills and competencies is related to the school, university, and the remaining theoretical and practical part is taken online, which expresses the meaning of the approach called "50+25+25". . This approach prevents students from spending too much time in classrooms and recording lectures. This aspect is one of the advantages of this approach. They get the professional knowledge and experience they need directly at the workplace, that is, through service interactions and direct observation of the work process with colleagues and mentors at universities and schools. This process makes up 50% of the knowledge, skills and competence acquired by the student. Also, acquiring the remaining 25% of knowledge, skills and qualifications online and another 25% in the form of traditional education ensures the acquisition of professional competencies based on theoretical knowledge and practical work experience. This helps shorten the period of professional adaptation of future specialists.

There are specific reasons for organizing the educational process using this approach. During the research, questionnaires were received from teachers working in educational

institutions. According to him, the majority of teachers (78%) said that young professionals who graduated from a higher education institution in a traditional way had difficulty applying the theoretical knowledge they learned at the workplace, this period of professional adaptation is about 2-5 years. who stated that the year will continue. In the approach we propose, this period of professional adaptation and the period of study at a higher educational institution will run parallel, and graduates will have the opportunity to continue their work in organizations as ready specialists. In our opinion, this approach ensures that students will further increase their knowledge and acquire professional qualities and qualities easily and quickly.

In our opinion, the transition to the "50+25+25" approach to education will help preserve the young workforce in our country, especially in the regions. After all, making an early decision on the training of personnel necessary for a specific educational organization, that is, universities and schools, and jointly developing the regulatory framework and standards for mastering this or that professional experience will help young professionals to their while supporting their personal initiative, it increases their employability. Students will have the opportunity to master their time through online learning and instruction, not in classrooms, but in their workplaces and on the Internet through gadgets. The main goal of this approach is to train tomorrow's specialists in future-oriented professions.

3. One of the methods effectively used in mixed education is "Traveling training". As we know from our pedagogical experience, the environment has a great impact on students. Organizing the lesson not only in the classroom, but also outside, increases students' abilities and enthusiasm for learning. A change in routine is well remembered. This experience is considered a "walking exercise" that helps you gain experience for the task at a later time. Teachers need to set this activity properly and connect it to the subject matter and the new environment, because the new place is inspiring and it helps the language learner to connect between the community and the curriculum. encourages. After the field trip, students can have a discussion to share what they learned during the field trip and highlight the importance of such a field trip.

It is appropriate to conduct the English language lesson using innovative technologies in the following way: this lesson is intended not only for students studying in the fields of "Design" and "Tourism", but also other fields of study. can be transferred between According to the working curriculum, students get to know the country of the language being studied, get an idea of its culture and traditions. It's no secret that independently acquired information is firmly stored in memory. The non-traditional form of lessons used in the classes - virtual travel increases the learning activity of students. Therefore, the virtual tour to the art collections of the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan fits both the program and the teaching profile. The lesson is held in a foreign language room equipped with modern information technologies, including the Internet. Students learn to independently acquire new knowledge and skills and apply them in practice with the help of the teacher with the help of information technologies (working with foreign language sites). Our research is that in our "traveling class" online, students can take virtual tours of art museums and places of interest, broadening their horizons and helping them understand the world around them.

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